

CYPRUS
SOCIETY OF
HUMAN
GENETICS

1ST INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
2 0 0 8

THE CYPRUS SOCIETY
OF HUMAN GENETICS

3-4 October, 2008
NICOSIA, CYPRUS

VENUE

Solon Triantafyllides Conference Hall
Bank of Cyprus, Agia Paraskevi
Nicosia, Cyprus
www.cshg.org.cy

OP10

The novel occurrence of corneal opacity in association with first case of Aicardi syndrome in the Arab

A. Al Mosawi

University Hospital in Al Kadhimiyia, Baghdad, Iraq

Email: almosawiAJ@yahoo.com

Background: Aicardi syndrome (AS), is a sporadic rare cerebro-ocular disorder that affects primarily females. It consists of cerebral manifestation including agenesis of the corpus callosum, seizures, and mental retardation. Ocular abnormalities include chorioretinal lacunae and microphthalmia. Corneal opacities have not been reported with this syndrome. The aim of this paper is to report. The novel occurrence of corneal opacity in association with first case of Aicardi syndrome in the Arab.

Patient and Method: 18 month old girl with bilateral microphthalmia and developmental delay was referred because her mother has become pregnant and there was fear of birth of another abnormal child. The girl has significant growth retardation with all of her growth parameters below the third centiles. She looks active and smiling frequently despite serious visual impairment. She doesn't say any word yet. She was able to sit from supine position but unable to stand. She has microcephaly (Head circumference 32cm), bilateral microphthalmia and bilateral corneal opacities, microphthalmia. Serological tests for congenital rubella, cytomegalovirus, toxoplasmosis were negative. She has normal female karyotype. Ultrasound of the eyes showed echogenic anterior segment, vitreal haziness and opacity. CT-scan of the brain showed prominent cistern magna, bilateral cerebral atrophy and agenesis of the corpus callosum. Abdominal ultrasound revealed normal findings.

Conclusion: The novel occurrence of corneal opacity in association with first case of AS in the Arab reported.

Keywords: Aicardi syndrome, Arab, corneal opacity.

PP1

A dysmorphic girl with acrocephaly, seizures, long fingers, and cherry red spots: a new association

A. Al Mosawi

University Hospital in Al Kadhimiyia, Baghdad, Iraq

Email: almosawiAJ@yahoo.com

Objective: To report the association of acrocephaly, cherry red spots, squint, seizures and long spindle fingers which has not been reported before.

Methods: A 10 month old girl with generalized tonic clonic convulsion despite treatment with sodium valproate and two of her siblings, a girl and boy were similar in appearance to this girl died from recurrent seizures that didn't respond to sodium valproate during the first year of life. Seizure was completely controlled with carbamazepine. The aim of this paper is to report a new clinical association.

Results: The girl was born at by term with average weight by normal vaginal delivery. The mother did not report taking any drugs during pregnancy. The girl was acrocephaly with flat occiput and has epicanthic fold and bilateral mild convergent squint. At the age of 10 month she didn't have any visible tooth. Her fingers were long and spindle in shape. All of her growth parameters were just below the third centiles. Fundoscopy examination showed bilateral macular cherry red spots. Cetavlon test for mucopolysachridosis was negative. Serum and urine chromatography showed no abnormal amino acids.

Conclusion: A new clinical association is reported.